

SAMARKAND AND THE GREAT SILK ROAD (TOURIST OPPORTUNITIES OF THE CITY)

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Annotation: The role of the Great Silk Road in the development of trade between countries over the centuries is incomparable. Many cities played a big role in the development of the Great Silk Road and trade. In particular, this article describes the importance of Samarkand's place on the Great Silk Road and the role of Samarkand as a special bridge in world cultural relations

Key words: colonial campaigns of the Russian Empire, Father Shepherd, von Kaufman, Amir Muzaffar, Zarafshan district, Samarkand region, General Abramov, new urban system, boulevard

Access: The restoration of the historical roads that passed through the territory of Uzbekistan serves the development of trade relations and tourism between the countries of Central Asia and within the country is doing This very basis requires the research of the historical Great Silk Roads based on the "New Silk Road" concept.

The main part: In today's globalization conditions, restoration of the Great Silk Road in Uzbekistan and development of the tourism sector are important in determining the economy of the regions. therefore, during the years of independence, a lot of work was done to improve this industry, and its educational and legal foundations were created. Also, since 1993, in cooperation with UNESCO and the International Trade Organization (ITO), seminars dedicated to tourism have been organized in order to develop international tourism. In addition, in October 1994, UNESCO and the International Trade Organization (ITO) organized an international seminar on "Development of tourism on the Great Silk Road" in Samarkand, with the participation of representatives of more than 20 countries, and important documents related to the field were adopted. but despite this, the available opportunities are not

fully used, the conditions created in tourism are not at the level of demand in the regions. This requires that the tourism infrastructure should be researched by region.

Samarkand region was established on January 15, 1938, and the regional center is the city of Samarkand. Its land area is 16.77 thousand square meters. is a kilometer. Administratively, Samarkand region consists of 14 districts, 12 cities and towns, and 1932 villages. Samarkand has an ancient history and occupies an important place in the history of the region. The geographical position of Samarkand is an important factor in determining its position in the region.

The oasis of Samarkand, which starts from the upper reaches of Zarafshan, is located in the Samarkand basin, and is surrounded by mountains such as Gubdintog-Oqtog-Koratog from the north and Karatepa-Zirabulok-Ziyovuddin from the south. the plains of this oasis are quite wide, narrowing only after the city of Navoi and forming the Hazar Corridor where the Kyziltepa and Oftobachi mountains converge. After that, the plain of the river valley widens again and changes its direction to the south-west. after that, Bukhara oasis begins. In the Bukhara oasis, the river flows almost through the plain, and the oasis turns into a natural plain. The oasis is surrounded by Kyzylkum from the north, Koshtepa, Azkamar, Kuyimozor, Kainagach, Kumsultan hills from the east, and the Karakol plateau from the south and southwest. the Zarafshan river starts from the border of Eastern Sughd and ends in Western Sughd - Bukhara.

these opportunities will have a good effect on the development of tourism in Samarkand. It is known from history that Samarkand was in the leading position in the region in terms of water quality.

Today, many natural, socio-economic and political factors play an important role in the organization and development of tourism in Samarkand. from this point of view, it is important for the development of international tourism to have a modern airport, roads, shopping malls, cultural recreation centers, and well-preserved city monuments. in addition, the agricultural and industrial sectors of the tourism-related economy, in particular, the food and textile industry, also have an impact on the development of this sector.

Today, modern tourism requires the creation of various services. At the same time, tourists need not only historical and architectural monuments, but also natural, religious, ethnographic tourism. Based on this, it is necessary to determine the influence of a number of factors on the organization and development of tourism in the city of Samarkand. In this regard, in particular, natural and socio-economic factors are in the leading position. Development of local tourism in Samarkand is also carried out by organizing 1-3 day routes around the city and adjacent areas, developing recreation and sports tourism in the foothills of the region. Now it can be seen that "domestic tourism" has revived a little compared to the first years of independence. An example of this is the fact that more and more people of our republic are traveling in groups.

Since 2005, the Tashkent-Samarkand high-speed trains named "Registon" and since 2014 "Afrosiyob" have been launched, allowing residents of the Fergana Valley, Tashkent city, and Tashkent region to come to Samarkand for a one-day trip.

About 150 historical-architectural monuments have been identified in the city of Samarkand, and historical-architectural examples similar to Samarkand can be found only in a few cities of the world (Rome, Athens, Cairo, etc.). That's why Samarkand is not called "Museum under the open sky" for nothing. In this city with such an opportunity, it is now necessary to develop new things, a new route and a program of excursions that will interest tourists.

Conclusion: Based on the above, the following conclusions and suggestions can be made:

- The natural conditions and relief of the city of Samarkand have been formed for centuries, and their use as a tourist object is important for the development of tourism. This indicates, firstly, the development of tourism in different directions in Samarkand, and secondly, that the region is rich in internal resources from a touristic geographical point of view;

- Viewing the historical monuments testifying to the long past of mankind greatly helps people to travel in imagination and learn the rich spiritual heritage left to us by our ancestors. For example, most of the world travelers travel to see historical

monuments in different countries of the world. In world international tourism, among cities like Rome, Paris, Beijing, Agra, Cairo, tourists who visit Samarkand also admire and enjoy the historical, architectural, construction, building and other places created by mankind. This is a proof that Samarkand is emerging as one of the cities in the world where tourism is developing.

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